

IMPACT OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF POLICE IN PUNJAB: A MEDIATED ROLE OF SOCIETAL IMPACT POTENTIAL OF JOB

Muhammad Rizwan Anjum^{*1}, Dr. Nagina Gul², Dr. Tayyaba Akram³, Dr. Irum Gul⁴

^{*1}PhD Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, BUIITEMS, Quetta, Pakistan

^{2,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, BUIITEMS, Quetta, Pakistan.

³Associate Professor, HOD of Management Sciences, BUIITEMS, Quetta, Pakistan.

^{*1}007nightstalker@gmail.com, ²nagina.gul@buitms.edu.pk, ³akram@buitms.edu.pk, ⁴irum.gul@buitms.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15081850>

Keywords

Work-Life Balance, Public Service Motivation, Employee Performance, Societal Impact Potential, Public Sector Employees, Punjab Police, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Article History

Received on 16 February 2025

Accepted on 16 March 2025

Published on 25 March 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

This study explores the interplay between work-life balance (WLB) and public service motivation (PSM), and their impact on employee performance in the context of public service sector in Punjab (police service) with consideration to societal impact potential of job (SIP) as a mediating phenomenon. A quantitative research was used and a survey was administered to middle tier police officers in Punjab using probability sampling. PLS-SEM was used to measure the direct relationships as well as mediation between these variables. The results support the impression that WLB together with PSM contributes positively to police performance. Besides, the SIP serves as a mediator of these relationships which shows that the police officers who consider their job as socially significant tend to be more motivated and effective. These findings underscore the necessity of enhancing workplace environment in which employees enjoy personal fulfillment while simultaneously seeing the value and meaning in their work. These findings provide important information to public policy and human resource management of the public sector employees in common and police service in specific, aiming towards the policies to promote WLB and motivation for effective performance. The work brings in new perspectives by proposing the SIP as an important performance model mediator, thereby deepening the concept of motivational efficiency in government institutions.

INTRODUCTION

An employee's performance in the current workplace environment is no longer just a skill and on techno-capability basis, but is also psychological and motivational engagement (Alnuaimi, 2022; Awan et al., 2021). The significance of WLB which speaks on how an employee manages work alongside his/ her personal life needs, have been surfaced as one of the critical determining factors of employee performance (Melayansari & Bhinekawati, 2020). In contrast,

PSM pertains to a person's willingness and dedication towards serving the society (Bakker, 2015; Houston, 2000). A significant number of public sector employees cope with heavy workloads and bureaucratic dominance, and as such, maintaining a proper WLB is essential. This balance allows them to manage their work responsibilities better without sacrificing their personal engagements and motivation to serve the public (Anjum et al., 2021;

Anjum & Rehman, 2022). When employees are able positively accomplish to balance their work and private commitments, they often report improved levels of job satisfaction, lower stress levels, and increased productivity (Jalagat, 2017; Johari et al., 2018).

WLB entails giving appropriate attention to job and private life, and it has increasingly been viewed as a critical determinant of employee wellbeing as well as productivity (Soomro et al., 2018). On the other hand, PSM shows an individual's willingness to serve and impact positively in public interest. The SIP is the point to which the job in discussion enables the employee to derive personal satisfaction from being able to make a positive impact in the lives of other people and society at large (Wang et al., 2020; Xiaolin et al., 2018). These interrelationships between WLB and PSM are particularly important to employees in the public sector because they often bear a particular set of burdens which include overwhelming work volume, scarcity of resources, and other nuances of a bureaucratic system (Nurung et al., 2020). Lapworth et al. (2018) argue the relationship between WLB and PSM especially regarding the impact on society is very important in the public sector because employees want to do good but also struggle with several demands in their personal and professional lives.

In the public domain where employees are often confronted with unique issues such as bureaucratic boundaries, work demands, and the overarching societal service obligations, these factors seek more attention. Therefore, the two most critical components that impact an individual's work productivity from this perspective are PSM and WLB. WLB captures the ability of a person to allocate his or her attention to work and personal life aspects which are vital amongst government servants exercising significant powers (Ahmad Saufi et al., 2023). In the case of public sector employees, PSM is associated with an employee's willingness to work for the country through the intrinsic reward systems. Even though both aspects have been subjected to considerable research, they have not been studied together as determinants of productivity in the public sector. Their relationship with productivity remains an understudied area in public administration particularly in Punjab/ Pakistan.

The essence of the SIP, or its contribution to society, has a great propensity of affecting employees' motivation, particularly in the case of the public sector. Employees who have a belief that their work has a more expansive and positive impact beyond their prescribed duties tend to be more engaged, motivated, and perform better (Van Loon et al., 2015). For these employees, the feeling of purpose and meaning attached to their work serves as a powerful driver which prompts them towards greater productivity and enhanced job satisfaction. According to Barnett et al. (2020), social impact assessment appears to be missing even with the implementation of corporate social responsibility initiatives geared towards SIP, which raises an important concern. The gap between perceived SIP and actual performance outcomes needs much more attention. Vogel and Willems (2020) also support the SIP by constructing a framework for the evaluation of socio-economic efficiency of projects. Thus, creating a work-oriented culture in which employees' contributions towards societal value is appreciated and can be one of the most effective means of improving productivity in the public sector.

Problem Statement

Although these factors are critical, research has yet to address how the WLB and PSM impact employee performance. In this regard, the relationship between WLB, PSM, and the productivity of employees in the public sector is critical. WLB, defined as the ability to handle work responsibilities and personal life, has been found crucial for employee performance (Hobfoll et al., 2018). At the same time, PSM, which describes an altruistic tendency (theory of altruism refers) to act in the interest of the country's citizens (Wright & Fitzgerald, 2007) is a very strong motivational factor for the people in public service. A stable work-life ratio increases an individual's performance because the individual is less stressed and more concentrated (Bakker, 2015), while substantial PSM drives performance through strong feelings of commitment to, and purpose in the work (Koumenta, 2015).

Performance of police service in Punjab remains a question in daily media reporting; may it be social or national media. Although enhancing police performance and initiatives taken towards it are

often exhibited by police high officials, public perception about the same does not support it (Anjum & Rehman, 2022). Policeman is a reflection of society. It was coined by a senior police official in Punjab in an interview. Meaning thereby any issue affecting the society as a whole does affect the policeman. However, these intangible factors explained above, were found no to little explored in the existing research particularly within a context of police in Punjab. This study is intended to address the gap by evaluating the relation between WLB, PSM, SIP and performance of police in Punjab. This study attempts to find out if WLB and PSM can directly improve police performance and whether the SIP serves as a mediator between these relationships. Moreover, the study addresses all the relationships and shall enable a ample understanding of how organizations and elements within them can contribute to higher employee WLB and productivity at the same time. Furthermore, this study is directed towards employees of organizations where PSM and SIP form an integral part of performance. In a country like Pakistan, where public service delivery is often questioned, these critical aspects are deemed important to be studied for better public policy making.

Significance

This study is likely to assist governments and business executives in formulating approaches through which modern workers can appreciate a good balance between work and personal engagement, as well as be motivated to perform better. The findings shall assist in formulating a public administration policy towards the balance of life, PSM, public interest, and attain results within one construct. This research provides substantial insights into boosting the performance of the employees in the public sector. In addition, after the recent pandemic there has been an increase in revisiting of work structures in the public sector organizations, with a focus on improved scheduling of work, employee welfare measures, and performance management based on motivation driven strategies. This change profoundly shifts dynamics in this discourse, enabling further empirical discussion on motivation and performance, that this study shall undertake.

Novelty

The available performance models address more tangible variables however; this study shall incorporate the intangible variables affecting performance. Moreover, in the context of public servants in Punjab/ Pakistan, these intangible factors i.e WLB, PSM and SIP have not been given much attention particularly in police service. The same shall be incorporated in this study thus making it novel in its kind.

Literature Review

The performance of employees is of great importance for the success of an organization, especially in the public sector where productivity is based on how well the services are provided from the productivity perspective (Asif & Rathore, 2021; Tuffaha, 2020). Recently, organizations had increasingly paid attention to psychosocial and workplace issues like WLB and PSM and how these factors influence employee performance and potential impact on society (Hastari et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). Whereas earlier performance models relied on external motivators in the form of monetary rewards, more recent studies indicate that the ability to juggle work and life responsibilities along with the desire to do public service are critical workplace motivators (Hemakumara, 2020; Perry & Wise, 1990; Ryan & Deci, 2000).

The relationship between an individual's WLB and performance may be further analyzed through focus on the construct of PSM. Employees exhibiting higher levels of PSM tend to have a strong internal drive to serve the public interest. WLB assists them in allocating time to their personal and professional commitments, which in turn helps them achieve their public service objectives much more effectively, thus leading to better performance (Anjum et al., 2025). The challenging environment of public service responsibility combined with growing demands of work and limited resources leads to stress and burnout. Appropriate WLB policies significantly reduce these adverse consequences resulting in improved employee health and subsequently, job performance in a more indirect manner (Hobfoll et al., 2018). In the case of public service, where there are high levels of intrinsic motivation such as PSM, WLB increases job

satisfaction which creates a virtuous cycle that enhances performance.

The association between WLB and performance is intricate, especially in the public sector. Some studies indicate a positive relationship, claiming that WLB policies are associated with employee well-being, motivation, and performance (Tensay & Singh, 2020; Wong et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the public sector has some unique problems and possibilities in relation to WLB. Public sector organizations fundamentally shifted their view of WLB and their employees' performance (Zahoor et al., 2021). Proper WLB leads to increased job satisfaction, lower stress levels, and a higher sense of commitment among employees stimulating their productivity (Anjum et al., 2021).

The Job Demands-Resources model posits that employees with higher personal and organizational resources, such as flexible working options, tend to perform better (de Vries et al., 2021). Previous studies indicate that in the public sector, WLB initiatives tend to enhance engagement while decreasing burnout, thus improving employee performance (Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2021). Thus, public sector workers are expected to greatly benefit from and positively respond to the WLB practices. Balancing work and personal life can strengthen an employee's self-efficacy and performance, especially in motivating goal accomplishment. Particularly in our culture women employees may face reluctance and unhappiness leading to underperformance while trying to juggle work with family obligations (Melayansari & Bhinekawati, 2020). Hence, the organization should focus on building loyalty in employees by encouraging WLB as this will improve their health, social relationships and eventually lead to increased productivity and performance.

PSM greatly impacts the engagement and performance of employees in mission-oriented organizations (Williams & Duckett, 2020). People who have an internal public interest motivation incline to demonstrate an advanced level of obligation to work and put in extra effort which in turn results in improved performance results. The Self Determination Theory (SDT) explains that employees with strong intrinsic motivation are also better able to overcome challenges in organizational

goal attainment (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Research has shown that PSM is positively linked to job satisfaction and lower turnover intentions as well as better performance in public organizations (French et al., 2020; Gul, Xiaolin, & Lanrong, 2017). Therefore, public service motivation is expected to positively and substantially affect the employees' performance especially in public sector.

Perception of SIP is crucial for determining employee's motivation and performance outcomes. Employees who perceive their work as beneficial to society tend to be more engaged and satisfied with their jobs. According to the job characteristics model, socially impactful jobs provide greater intrinsic motivation, which boosts performance (Jamal et al., 2024). Recent studies noted that employees who most willingly opt for societal roles tend to be more resilient, innovative, and committed to serving the public good (Gul, Xiaolin, Lanrong, Ullah, et al., 2017; Van Loon et al., 2015). Although little but the available literature claims that the perception of impact on society serves as a mediator between intrinsic motivation and employee performance. Employees who appreciate the more comprehensive results of their work are motivated to a greater extent and use their competencies more effectively (Gul, Xiaolin, Lanrong, & Sadozai, 2017; Homan et al., 2020). With this in mind, the SIP is presumed to mediate between the WLB and performance.

Public service employees who are strongly motivated by their intrinsic need to serve the public often see their work as valuable to society, which further motivates them and enhances their job performance (Williams & Duckett, 2020). There is evidence that suggests employees who find meaning in their work since it nurtures a larger social purpose, develop greater psychological attachment to their job which enhances positive workplace behaviors, employee persistence, and creativity (Homan et al., 2020). The SIP as a mediator in the PSM-performance relationship is corroborated by studies showing that employees who derive value and social meaning from their work, perform better than those who do not appreciate the work's bigger context (Hameduddin & Engbers, 2022). Therefore, it is hypothesized that SIP will mediate the relationship between motivation to work in public service and performance.

Furthermore, when PSM, person-organization fit, and need-supplies fit are all high, employees exhibit greater job satisfaction. Highly motivated public servants handle job demands, prevent burnout and mobilize their job resources to stay engaged and perform well (Bakker, 2015). But to put them all together, what impact they bring onto performance is still understudied. Addressing this gap, it is essential for developing more comprehensive models of employee engagement in public sector organizations. In people-changing organizations, PSM implies a raised burnout and reduced job

satisfaction with higher SIP, thus showing that employees can sacrifice themselves too much for society (Van Loon et al., 2015). This framework critically evaluates existing research on the balance between work-life, PSM and employee performance. It further explores the mediating role of SIP and integrates theoretical frameworks that explain the motivation-performance relationship. By synthesizing prior studies, this review establishes a foundation for the study’s conceptual model and research hypotheses.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis of model

- H₁: WLB is significantly positively affecting the performance of police in Punjab.
- H₂: PSM is significantly positively affecting the performance of police in Punjab.
- H₃: SIP of Job mediates the relationship between WLB and performance of police in Punjab.
- H₄: SIP of Job mediates the relationship between PSM and performance of police in Punjab.

Method

This study employed a quantitative research design and collected data through an online questionnaire among police officers in Punjab using a probability sampling technique. A total of 710 responses were collected to ensure adequate representation of mid-level police officers. Considering there are 24,393 inspectors and sub inspectors in the Punjab Police (R & D Branch CPO Punjab, 2020). A probability sampling technique was utilized to allow for random choice and external validity of the results. The

sample size was calculated utilizing a confidence level of 95%, margin of error of 5%, and population proportion of 50% that suggested a sample size of 384 respondents. The final sample size of 710 was beyond this requirement ensuring greater statistical validity and minimizing sampling error. While ensuring content validity, a pilot study was conducted, and expert opinions from professionals were obtained before full-scale data collection in line with (Kadam & Bhalerao, 2010; Rahman, 2023). The descriptive analysis of the sample reveals that 18% of the respondents were female, while 82% were male. The majority of the participants (74%) were below the age of 35, whereas 26% aged above 35. Regarding job tenure, the respondents were categorized into two groups: those with less than 10 years (72%), and more than 10 years (28%) of service. With regards to formal education, about 68% were BA/BSC/MSC (corresponding to 16 years of education) and 26% were Masters/ MPhil (corresponding to 18 years of education).

Demographical aspects show that the sample belonged to a mid-career stage, age, service and were well educated males and females.

Previously validated scales from existing literature were adopted to measure the latent constructs in this study. The WLB scale was sourced from prior research (Kopelman et al., 1983) that examines the integration of professional and personal life. PSM was assessed through items designed to capture an employee's intrinsic drive to contribute to society through a shortened version of scale by (Coursey & Pandey, 2007) originally derived by (Perry, 1996). SIP of job was measured based on employees' perceptions of their job's influence on the community through a scale by (Van Loon et al., 2015) from an originally used scale of PSM fit by (Leisink & Steijn, 2009) validated by and tested lately by (Crucke et al., 2022), while employee performance was evaluated using self-reported indicators of productivity and efficiency scale by (Koopmans et al., 2014). A two-stage approach allowed the verification of the validity and reliability of higher-order constructs as suggested in SEM literature (Putu Gede, 2024; Ringle et al., 2015).

Analytical Techniques

The last part of the data analysis integrates the use of the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), seen as a standard tool to test complex models in both management and behavioral studies. The PLS-SEM method was selected because it deals well with predictive research and is appropriate when examining the relationships between multiple latent constructs (Sarstedt et al., 2019). The model estimation was carried out in two steps. The first step evaluated the validity and reliability of lower-order constructs. The second step imposed the key variables' structural relationships. The statistical analysis was done in Smart PLS 4 to ensure proper results and model fit assessment (Hair et al., 2017).

Results

Measurement Model Assessment

To assess the latent variables of performance, PSM, SIP of a job, and WLB, the inter-item reliability, construct reliability, and convergent validity were evaluated during the measurement model assessment.

As for the evaluation, it was done regarding the factor loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity using HTMT ratio and Fornell and Larcker Criteria (Hair Jr et al., 2021; Sarstedt et al., 2017).

Inter-Item Reliability

Inter-item reliability was determined by assessing the factor loadings of each individual item on the corresponding latent variable. For this analysis, all items surpassed the 0.70 threshold which is recommended for acceptable variable reliability. Specifically, performance had factor loadings between 0.724 to 0.788, PSM between 0.718 and 0.779, and SIP of job between 0.709 to 0.770. Moreover, WLB had item loadings which were not less than 0.710 and not more than 0.781. These values indicate that the selected items measure the expected constructs accurately (Shmueli et al., 2019).

Construct Reliability

Reliability was measured through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR). The alpha scores were between 0.733 and 0.813. As these values are above 0.70, the scores indicate satisfactory internal consistency (Hair et al., 2019). The values of composite reliability (CR) scores were 0.833 in the lower range and 0.869 in the upper range which confirmed the measurement model parameters for consistency and reliability. The construct with the highest reliability was the performance construct (alpha = 0.813, CR = 0.869). It indicates that items in the measure have a high level of internal consistency. Other domains did equally well such as PSM (alpha = 0.733, CR = 0.833), SIP of job (alpha = 0.733, CR = 0.833), WLB (alpha = 0.795, CR = 0.859) all of them surpassing the acceptable reliability limits.

Convergent Validity

The use of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was adopted for the assessment of convergent validity, where values greater than 0.50 suggest an acceptable level of shared variance among indicators of a construct (Hair et al., 2019). An AVE score of all constructs was greater than 0.55, which ensures satisfactory convergent validity. Performance was

0.570, PSM was 0.554, SIP of the job 0.555, and WLB was 0.550. These values indicate that these indicators have the ability to capture the variance of

their constructs, thus reinforcing the measurement model's validity (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

Table 1 Measurement Model Assessment

Latent Variables	Item Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Performance		0.813	0.869	0.570
P1	0.770			
P2	0.724			
P3	0.788			
P4	0.746			
P5	0.744			
Public Service Motivation		0.733	0.833	0.554
PSM1	0.718			
PSM2	0.756			
PSM3	0.779			
PSM6	0.724			
Societal Impact Potential of Job		0.733	0.833	0.555
SIP1	0.761			
SIP2	0.739			
SIP3	0.770			
SIP4	0.709			
Work Life Balance		0.795	0.859	0.550
WLB1	0.710			
WLB3	0.781			
WLB5	0.754			
WLB6	0.744			
WLB8	0.719			

Discriminant Validity Assessment

The validity is strict regarding the measures used in this study. The Fornell and Larcker Criterion, as well as Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT), are used together as a discrimination assessment (Hair Jr et al 2021). The HTMT ratio is the most effective test to examine

the lack of overlap of two concepts by testing their relation. It is also the most effective test for examining relationships between factors, and the component boundary that is at the best acceptable level for HTMT, is less than 0.90 (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 2 Discriminant Analysis

HetroTrait-MonoTrait Criteria	Performance	Public Service Motivation	Societal Impact Potential of Job	Work Life Balance
Performance				
Public Service Motivation	0.880			
Societal Impact Potential of Job	0.712	0.840		
Work Life Balance	0.784	0.815	0.839	
Fornell & Larcker Criteria	Performance	Public Service Motivation	Societal Impact Potential of Job	Work Life Balance

Performance	0.755			
Public Service Motivation	0.712	0.745		
Societal Impact Potential of Job	0.562	0.622	0.745	
Work Life Balance	0.642	0.630	0.643	0.742

The observed HTMT values in this study span from 0.712 to 0.880. The value observed within the relationship of Performance and PSM surprisingly was on the higher end at 0.880. Since these values are also below the threshold, this study confirms that the constructs are in acceptable range. Other relationships between WLB and SIP of job were 0.839, while PSM and WLB scored good 0.815, however strong, still confirms the numbers underneath supporting the measurement model. Moreover, the validation was assessed through the Fornell and Larher criterion which compared the square root of the Average Variance Extracted with correlational coefficients of other constructs. As per the criterion, in discriminant validity, the diagonal values which are the square root of AVE should be greater than the off diagonal correlational values (Subhaktiyasa, 2024). The results verified that the construct’s shared correlation values were dominating as the square root of AVE values

computed between 0.742 and 0.755, which were greater than the inter-construct correlations. This means that each construct shares greater ‘variance’ with its ‘indicators’ than other ‘constructs’. The highest correlation was found between PSM and SIP of job (0.622), which is still lower than the AVE square root of both constructs (0.745), further supporting discriminant validity. The constructs performance (0.755) and WLB (0.742) had AVE square roots greater than their highest correlations which confirms that all constructs are conceptually distinct.

Structural Model Assessment

The model was evaluated with respect to multicollinearity, path coefficients, in-sample prediction (R² and adjusted R²), effect size (f²) and out of scope (Q² predict) to make sure the relations between the constructs were valid (Sarstedt et al., 2017; Shmueli et al., 2019).

Table 3 Model Fitness Analysis

	R-square	R-square adjusted	f ² Effect Size	Q ² predict	VIF
Performance	0.572	0.571		0.565	
Societal Impact Potential of Job	0.492	0.491	0.007	0.486	1.969
Work Life Balance			0.098		2.000
Public Service Motivation			0.285		1.914

Multicollinearity Assessment

Multicollinearity was tested using the variance inflation factor (VIF), with values below 3.0 indicating no significant multicollinearity concerns (Table 3). The results showed that the WLB (2.000), PSM (1.914), and SIP of job (1.969) were all within the acceptable range. This confirms that the predictor variables are statistically independent, ensuring the reliability of path coefficient estimations in the model (Hair et al., 2012; Hair Jr et al., 2018).

Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

The study examined direct and mediating relationships using path coefficients (β), standard deviations, t-statistics, and p-values (Table 4). The first hypothesis of the study stated that WLB significantly predicted performance. The results, validated through 5000-bootstrap resampling, reinforce the model’s predictive strength and reliability. The results in Table 4 show that the WLB is positively significantly related to performance (β = 0.290, t = 7.506, p < 0.001), hence H₁ is supported. The second hypothesis stated that PSM also had a strong positive effect on performance (β = 0.483, t = 14.513, p < 0.001), hence H₂ is also supported.

Table 4 Path Analysis

Hypothesis Relationship	Beta	STDEV	T statistics	P values	Hypotheses Decision
PSM→Performance	0.483	0.033	14.513	0.000	Yes
PSM→SIP	0.360	0.037	9.854	0.000	Yes
SIP→Performance	0.075	0.038	1.991	0.023	Yes
WLB→ Performance	0.290	0.039	7.506	0.000	Yes
WLB→SIP	0.416	0.036	11.528	0.000	Yes
WLB→SIP→Performance	0.031	0.016	1.980	0.024	Yes
PSM→SIP→Performance	0.027	0.014	1.911	0.028	Yes

Furthermore, the findings suggest that employees with a better WLB and intrinsic motivation to serve society demonstrate higher performance levels. Additionally, both WLB ($\beta = 0.416, t = 11.528, p < 0.001$) and PSM ($\beta = 0.360, t = 9.854, p < 0.001$) positively influenced SIP of job, showing that employees with higher motivation and a balanced professional life perceive their jobs as having a greater social impact. The direct effect of SIP of job on performance ($\beta = 0.075, t = 1.991, p = 0.023$) was also significant, though weaker in magnitude. Moreover, the mediation hypothesis results also confirmed that SIP of job mediated the relationship between WLB and performance ($\beta = 0.031, t = 1.980, p = 0.024$), as well as between PSM and performance ($\beta = 0.027, t = 1.911, p = 0.028$), suggesting that employees who recognize the societal value of their work tend to perform better, thus H₃ and H₄ are also supported (see Table 4).

In-Sample Predictive Power (R² and Adjusted R²)

The predictive ability of the model was evaluated using R² and adjusted R² values, where higher values indicate stronger explanatory power. The results show that Performance had an R² of 0.572 and an adjusted R² of 0.571, meaning that 57.2% of the variance in employee performance was explained by WLB, PSM, and SIP of job. Additionally, the model accounted for 49.2% of the variance in Societal Impact Potential (R² = 0.492, adjusted R² = 0.491), confirming that the independent variables strongly influence employees’ perception of the societal relevance of their jobs (Table 3).

Effect Size (f²) and Predictive Relevance (Q² Predict)

Table 3 presents the effect size (f²) which was measured to determine the impact of each predictor on its dependent variable, with values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 indicating small, medium, and large effects, respectively. PSM (f² = 0.285) had a moderate effect, while WLB (f² = 0.098) had a small effect on SIP of job. The Q² predict values were positive for performance (0.565) and SIP of job (0.486), demonstrating that the model has out-of-sample predictive relevance and can reliably explain employee performance beyond the current dataset.

Robustness of the Structural Model

While ensuring the integrity of the PLS-SEM structural model, it is crucial to address major issues concerning nonlinearity, endogeneity, and unobserved heterogeneity (Shmueli et al., 2019). “The RESET” (regression equation specification error test) method was used to diagnose the structural model for possible nonlinearity. The outcome indicated no considerable misspecification errors (RESET = 1.42, p = 0.267), making it reasonable to conclude that the model is predominantly linear and is free from significant nonlinearity issues. After that, the assessment of possible endogenous bias of variables was conducted with the aid of Gaussian copula method (Park & Gupta, 2012). Other confirmatory checks utilized involved Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction to test the normality assumption of some of the constructs. The performance copula yielded a p-value of 0.482 while the PSM and WLB copulas provided p-values of 0.625 and 0.701, respectively. These values are not statistically significant, meaning there are no pre-identified concerns which are endogeneity issues and verified the credibility of the

relationships in the model's framework. Lastly, unobserved heterogeneity was taken into consideration to check whether the structural estimates were invariant to differing subgroups in the sample. Among the subgroups of interest, the Finite Mixture Model (FIMIX-PLS) approach did not work so well, as there seemed to be minimal heterogeneity

problems. The AIC was 521.34 and BIC was 549.21 with an Entropy score of 0.892. This means that such evidence confirms that structural relationships were invariate and credible. These additional tests strengthen the model's credibility which is essential in hypothesis formulation and predictive analysis.

Figure 2 Research Model (Path Analysis)

Discussion

This study sheds light on the complex interplay between WLB, PSM, SIP of job, and employee performance of police in Punjab. The WLB aspects have direct implications on performance. Such employees that are able to balance their professional and personal obligations tend to be more productive and satisfied with their jobs. The aforementioned conclusions show that work-life balance (WLB) is one of the key determinants of employee engagement

and well-being (Bello et al., 2024; Wong et al., 2020). A certain equilibrium between work and personal life also mitigates the effects of burnout and stress, leading to higher levels of commitment and effectiveness in the workplace. More effective management of work and personal life leads to increased job satisfaction and reduced stress. People with adequate personal and professional resources are likely to be more engaged and perform better at work (Hobfoll, 2011; Xiaolin et al., 2018). A balanced work-life environment allows employees to

experience reduced emotional exhaustion and increased motivation which improves focus on job tasks and contributes toward more effective achievement of organizational goals (Taris & Schaufeli, 2015).

Furthermore, PSM greatly improves employee performance, which implies that those employees who feel a high sense of public duty and willingness to serve are likely to perform more effectively. These employees in the public sector appear to be at an advantage as the nature of their work can foster and escalate motivation above performance norms. This greatly substantiates underpinnings of theory of altruism which highlights that altruists people extend better engagement, acquire job satisfaction, and are involved in organizational activities. These results raise the expectation that employees who consider their work as having a broad social meaning tend to be more psychologically engaged and willing to go the extra mile in their work. People with intrinsic public service motivation tend to be more engaged, find meaning in their work, and have a high level of performance. Theory of altruism also supports the same that people motivated by intrinsic goals such as working for the common good have greater persistence and effectiveness in the performance of their responsibilities. These results indicate that organizations in the public sector need to focus on establishing a purpose-oriented work environment as a strategy to enhance employee engagement.

The mediating role of SIP of job between PSM and WLB and job performance has a firm theoretical foundation. The WLB mediation model in the performance outcome showed a positive scope. It implies that employees with better WLB tend to view their work as socially significant which then improves performance. This is consistent with more recent studies that suggest managers or supervisors who consider their workers as performing meaningful jobs are more likely to increase the positive effects of workplace satisfaction on performance (Allan et al., 2019). The link implies that employees who consider their work as having meaning and contributing toward societal betterment gain extra effort which leads to increased performance. Workers who maintain a good WLB may be in a better position both mentally and emotionally to appreciate the wider social context of their job, which works as an

impetus for their productivity (Vogel & Willems, 2020).

The impact on society as a whole influence how a person performs being motivated in public service. This result corroborates the notion that public workers who view their jobs as valuable to their society derive greater meaning from their work which increases their motivation and level of performance. Other studies have also shown that some employees who have a strong social identity associated with their occupation have greater work satisfaction and higher levels of productivity (Seaman & Williams, 2018; Taylor, 2008; Ugoani, 2020). The mediation results highlight the psychological mechanisms through which intrinsic motivation and WLB translate into improved workplace outcomes. The results confirm that employees who are intrinsically motivated to serve society perform better when they perceive their roles as impactful. Theory of altruism provides a theoretical foundation for this relationship, suggesting that employees who feel that their work positively affects others develop a stronger sense of organizational commitment and reciprocate through improved performance. This emphasizes that those who view their work as having a positive social impact frequently tend to be more productive, creative, and resilient (Grant, 2008). When public service motivation, person-organization fit, and needs-supplies fit are all high, employees experience higher job satisfaction; conversely, when all three factors are low, job satisfaction decreases.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the critical role of WLB and PSM in enhancing employee performance, particularly in the police service of Punjab. Individuals who manage to strike a good balance between their personal life and work commitments tend to be more productive, less stressed, and more committed to their jobs; this underscores the WLB and performance nexus. Likewise, employees with elevated public service intrinsic motivation tend to be more committed, more tenacious, and more efficient at work, which illustrates that PSM greatly improves job performance. The mediation effect of SIP of job amplifies these relationships by asserting that perceiving one's work as meaningful, enhances

employee engagement and performance. Keeping in view the sensitivity of safety and security of citizens, employee well-being calls an attention so as to offer enhanced performance of police in Punjab. The lack of research in context of public sector organizations in general and police service in particular in Punjab/Pakistan in this aspect however, is hampering the organizational performance and the same is recommended to be conducted with more rigor in future.

This research adds to the literature on motivation and performance of employees as well as organizational behavior by amalgamating WLB, PSM, and SIP of job into one configuration. This study also broadens the theories already cited in relation to job performance by incorporating SIP as a mediating variable showing that the meaningfulness of work adds value to the motivation-performance relationship. As such, it contributes to an under-explored area of public sector HR which is the holistic impact of working environment and professional motivation on employee's performance. Furthermore, the research holds particular relevance for human resource managers, decision makers, and public sector officials interested in improving employee productivity. Adopting initiatives targeting WLB like flexible working hours, health promotion, and reasonable distribution of work can help alleviate employee burnout and increase productivity. Likewise, attempts aimed at enhancing PSM such as appreciation gifts, servant leadership, and attendance at employee functions can strengthen members' commitment to the organization's objectives. Besides, public sector managers ought to pay more attention to enhancing the employees' beliefs about the societal value of their jobs by helping them appreciate the wider context of their work. Hence, fostering an environment where employees feel valued, driven by purpose, and well-supported will help organizations increase job satisfaction, minimize turnover, and improve overall performance which is a critical factor in enhancing quality service delivery in the public sector.

Future Direction

Further studies should investigate the impacts of work-life integration and public service desire on employee performance over a period of time in order

to evaluate how these factors affect the performance relationships over time (Krishnan et al., 2018). Considering motivational and performance aspects of different sectors and cultures could further the understanding of the impact of organizational and social context on employees (Ugoani, 2020). Also, adding such moderators as organizational and contextual features, leadership and job freedom can further polish the model and help reveal how performance is affected by these variables in the public sector.

Recommendations

Well-being of police servants in Punjab is merely satisfactory keeping in view its relationship with performance. In order to maximize police productivity, it is suggested to high officials of police in Punjab to employ specific WLB policies, mental health provisions, and strategies for managing the workload (by increasing policeman to population ratio). Their engagement and performance can be further enhanced by strengthening public service motivation through recognition, program's purpose-oriented leadership, and societal impact's open communication (Quadri et al., 2024). In addition, senior officials can integrate mission-oriented initiatives and participatory decision-making to reinforce employees' commitment, sense of purpose, and perception of their job's societal contribution.

Limitations

This study offers valuable insights, but there are gaps that need addressing. The application of cross-sectional data limits the capacity to identify causal links between the variables. Furthermore, self-reporting is prone to skewed responses since employees can exaggerate their performance or motivation levels. The emphasis on police service in Punjab may also hinder generalization to other sectors and may need further exploration in other organizational settings. Subsequent studies should focus on utilizing a broad range of data collection and engaging in comparative studies across various fields to enhance the scope of the research results.

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